

**TRANSLATION OF REALITIES, PHRASEOLOGICAL
COMBINATIONS, PROVERBS AND SAYINGS IN WRITTEN
TRANSLATION**

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Abstract: This article presents comments on translation of realities, phraseological combinations, proverbs and sayings in written translation.

Key words: phraseology, translation studies, phrase, speech, knowledge, concept, lexicon, aphorisms, wise sayings.

The term "phraseology" expresses the meaning of a phrase, speech, knowledge, concept. Phraseology was formed as a separate part of linguistics not long ago, but the history of its origin goes back to the first stages of language development. It is known from scientific studies that phraseological units appeared together with the language and developed together with the language. But in different eras of society, their place and importance are evaluated differently. Phraseologisms are linguistic units with structure, lexical-semantic, functional-stylistic and syntactic functions, as well as specific formation features.

In linguistics, the term "phraseology" was used by the French linguist Charles Bally and studied in conjunction with the science of stylistics. But the well-known linguist scientist prof. E. F. Polivanov expressed the opinion of recognizing phraseology as a science. Academician V. is another scientist who supports this opinion. V. Vinogradov. In a number of his scientific studies, he studied phraseological compounds in the Russian language and grouped them semantically.

E. D. Polivanov and V. V. Vinogradov's ideas about phraseology later inspired many studies in this field. But until now, the opinions about whether or not

to consider phraseology as a science have not been fully resolved. For example, those who understand the scope of phraseology in a narrow sense do not include proverbs, aphorisms and wise sayings in phraseologisms, saying that it is necessary to study only the phrases themselves. Some scientists consider phraseological combinations to be the equivalent of words and include them in lexicology. Professor Sh. Rahmatullaev also agreed with this opinion: "Vocabulary is made up of words and phrases formed on the basis of these words. As vocabulary, words are called lexical units, and phrases are called phraseological units. These are summarized and referred to as a lexical unit. The phrase serves to mean a dictionary meaning. Accordingly, it is considered a lexical unit and in this respect it is placed along with the word," he says.

Many scientists agree with this opinion. M. Sodikova understands phraseology in a broad sense and includes proverbs and proverbs in the "Russian-Uzbek Phraseological Dictionary" compiled by herself. Ya., who included figurative expressions, proverbs, wise words and idiomatic combinations in the phraseological composition. D. Pinkhasov also joins the ranks of those who understand phraseology in a broad sense. Also Q. Musaev also supports this second opinion. We agree with this opinion and understand phraseologism in a broad sense and consider free phrases in translation as phraseologisms.

In Uzbek linguistics, the issues of the formation of English phraseological units have not been thoroughly studied. Before studying the features of the formation of phraseology of both languages, it is necessary to determine the status of the term phraseological formation. Phraseological formation studies the specific features and laws of forming phraseologisms with the help of language tools. Phraseological formation is close to word formation according to its goals and tasks. The process of formation of new words in word formation, and formation of new phraseology in phraseological formation is studied.

The process of translating phraseological units is not easy, because this process includes several factors. These are different combinations of words, homonyms,

synonyms and phraseological units expressing different meanings, polysemy, etc. In addition, phraseological units have stylistic coloring belonging to a certain nation, which may not be found in some languages. When understanding the basis of phraseology, it is necessary to remember the above. There are the following types of phraseological units: phrasemes and idioms. Phrases are context-dependent and units composed of specific indicators. And idioms are lexical units that determine the general meaning in the context, determine the completeness and equality of subordinate and defining elements. Each type and form of phraseological units can be considered a specific microstructure. During their translation, functional, equal linguistic units are selected by comparing the two languages. The principle of comparison shows the similarities and differences between the two. Some parts of this system are equivalent in form (partially or completely), and some of them may not have an alternative at all. A proverb is one of the genres of folklore with a compact form and deep content, which was created on the basis of centuries-old life observations, socio-economic, political and cultural experiences of the people.

A proverb is an admonition of the people, a spiritual and moral conclusion, an echo of the national spirit of the people, a wise criterion of the nature of the language. A proverb is not woven, but is created by the requirements of certain circumstances. The proverb has deep social, moral and philosophical content. Therefore, some proverbs can express the content of an entire novel or drama. For example, N. V. Gogol's proverb "If your head is crooked, don't lunge from the window" as an epigraph to Gogol's comedy "The Inspector" rings from the beginning to the end of the work. All the actions of the mayor Khlestakov, Dobchinsky, Bobchinsky and other figures and characters remind of this proverb. A folk proverb is a specific code of moral rules that everyone should follow. The proverbs express the conclusion of valuable thoughts resulting from life experiences. Proverbs often have a poetic form. They differ from other types of folk art by their conciseness, maturity and thoroughness.

According to their social and ideological functions, proverbs mainly represent the world views of the general public, and in some cases, of certain social classes or groups. Therefore, the thematic scope of proverbs is very wide, and this scope cannot be limited to the sphere of real life reality. There is no area of social existence that is not reflected in proverbs.

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